

TECHNOLOGY OF PREPARING FUTURE SPECIALISTS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY BASED ON THE MASTER- PUBLIC SYSTEM

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Abstract. *It is known that the technology of preparing future specialists for professional activity based on the mentor-apprentice system affects their moral and psychological state. The article describes the aesthetic and spiritual impact of the teacher-student system on the education of students, as well as the tasks of teachers and students.*

Keywords: *specialist, field, upbringing, person, attendance, value, generation, opportunity, education.*

In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the word "mentor" means a guide, an educator, a trainer, a guide, a teacher, a teacher [1].

In the peoples of the ancient East, the honor and respect of those who are called teachers, mentors, teachers, educators have always been high. From the time when man became aware of himself, he relied on teachers and received spiritual power from them. If a talented teacher does not create his own school, if he does not leave behind him knowledgeable and talented students, his life will be wasted. No matter how great a teacher is, no matter how much success he achieves in the educational process, if he does not leave his knowledge experience with reliable students, his achievements will disappear without a trace like a stone falling into water. Therefore, the name "teacher" is a word with a broad meaning, and a person who is worthy of this name is assigned a high responsibility in every way. That is why there are many instructive stories among the people about the respect of teachers. This means that the owner of any profession cannot be formed without a mentor, cannot find his place in life [2].

The tasks, responsibilities and obligations of students - apprentices are as follows:

- to have enough theoretical knowledge to become a highly qualified specialist in the chosen specialty;

- to collect, study and update information about the position of one's field and specialty in the Republic and the world, production capacities, requirements for the position, development progress of the field;

- to increase responsibility for spiritual and moral education, to personally control one's lifestyle in order to become a perfect person, to be polite to friends and the community, and to be an example in all respects;

- to regularly expand research on mastering level, attendance, and specialization, studying national values and traditions in depth and continuing them;

- to be a promoter of the feeling of Motherland and national values among classmates, students, and to form the spiritual capabilities of oneself and others to educate the next generation;

- reconciliation of personal interests with the interests of society;

- Protecting the motherland, educational institution, its team and teacher and one's own honor, symbols of national pride and faith;

- it is to find one's place in the production already during the student period by gaining deep knowledge and skills in the chosen specialty and other subjects with deep attention to independent education.

The scientific research of scientists shows that the "Master-Apprentice" training system has a rich experience in teaching crafts to young people. However, in recent times, the rich heritage and experience of our ancestors is not being fully used. One of the reasons for this is the complete or partial knowledge of the Master-Apprentice system.

There are not enough textbooks and resources that study the rich heritage and experiences of our ancestors. In addition, future specialists who are currently studying for professional activities do not master the rules of oriental etiquette, which has a negative effect on knowledge and behavior, and in general, their participation in the formation of the spirituality of the young generation is insufficient.

Therefore, we should make good use of the rich spiritual heritage left by our ancestors: in particular, the developed model of the rules of the relationship between the teacher and the student gives the student the following personal and professional qualities:

- respect for the rich heritage of ancestors;
- strengthens respect for the older generation, comrades;
- forms universal human values;
- contributes to the full study of the basics of craft, subtleties of the work being studied.

It is known that the technology of preparing future specialists for professional activity based on the mentor-apprentice system affects their moral and psychological state. It should be noted that the master-disciple system has a unique effect on a person and cannot be replaced by anything else, that is, it has an aesthetic and spiritual effect on a person, that is why it is widely spread and used among the people.

Practical training conducted in the "Master and Apprentice" system includes the following tasks:

- increases the cultural and aesthetic level of the student:
- increasing interest in practical work, studying the history of decorative and practical art:
- getting to know the life and work of artisans:
- teaching students to work with various raw materials and produce finished products:
- forms the ability to creatively approach the studied subject, provides in-depth knowledge:
- prepares the student as a master of his work, a professional master of practical work.

The daily program of practical training introduces the student to the aesthetic, continuous work process. The technology of preparing future specialists for professional activities based on the mentor-apprentice system is aimed at acquiring professional knowledge, skills and qualifications in accordance with state educational standards, and its main purpose is:

- maintenance of physical, mental and social health of students;
- implementation of the principle of continuity of education, which contributes to the integrity of students' perception of the world;
- strengthening the health of students by introducing a professional education program;
- creating an atmosphere of creative cooperation, mutual understanding and mutual support in the educational process;

- increase in personal achievements of all participants of the educational process;
- ensuring the high level of knowledge of the graduate and continuity of cultural and historical traditions in the educational system.

The technology of preparing future specialists for professional activities based on the mentor-apprentice system, developing thinking, imagination, freedom, independence and freedom of behavior; includes the use of a system of methods that awakens not only intellectual, but also emotional activity of the student. Any activity, including teacher-apprentice activity, is determined not only by the child's formation of methods of professional activity, but also by the presence of appropriate objects and tools and the ability to use them in practical activities. Therefore, preparation for professional activities based on the mentor-apprentice system requires a system of material objects, enrichment of the basis of activity for the development of the student's personality, acquisition of professional knowledge, skills and qualifications in accordance with state educational standards.

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